

An animal rewarding scheme with adaptive methods for measuring sensory, or cognitive, or decision biases in behavioural experiments

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Abstract

Behavioural experiments in animals, in particular psychophysics measures of sensory processing, have been used to demonstrate similar illusory percepts in animals as in humans. These measures suffer from methodological shortcomings that can be argued to create unnecessary biases in the results or interpretation difficulties. In this paper, a method is presented that allows to measure the subjective percept of the tested subject. It combines psychophysics adaptive algorithms with a modified rewarding scheme. It is further argued that this method permits measures of any type of perceptual, cognitive, or response biases that can be of interest to investigate.

Introduction

Investigations on the visual systems of humans and animals aim at understanding how our and animals' perceptual world is created on the basis of the brain structures and functions. One of the approaches is through simplified behavioural measures of visual paradigms that target fundamental questions about cognitive and perceptual capacities of the tested subjects, which bring information on cross-species similarities and differences [1-5].

An interesting and useful probe of visual perception are visual illusions or misperceptions. Nowadays, despite differences in neuronal structures and sensory processing between species, multiple types of illusions have been demonstrated in varieties of animals [2,4,6-10]. These visual effects have become tools for understanding basic neuronal processing of visual information in human [11] or its closest neurophysiological model, the monkey, but also about cross-species general rules of visual information processing [12].

Experiments with illusory percepts, or conditions with misperception effects, are easily carried with human subjects. This is due to the fact that the experimenter can instruct the human subjects about the experiment and task, train the subjects, and receive feedback from the tested subjects in cases of not clear situations or misunderstanding.

In animals such measurements are more tricky. The illusory condition creates a situation where the animal's percept is putatively different from the physical input. Experiments with animals are carried first through a learning procedure that aims to teach them the experimental situation, task, and rewarding scheme, and the animals learn to respond to the physical attributes of the stimuli which are of relevance for the experiment. Thus, a problem appears when one needs to measure illusory or misperception conditions. The animal is rewarded for the physical attribute of the stimulus and this creates cognitive/decision biases in conditions with illusions or misperceptions. Various authors have used clever experimental modifications by introducing low number of trials of illusory conditions or other techniques (e.g. [1,6,7,13]). These methods were sufficient for demonstrating that, indeed, many animal species, not only humans, do have illusory percepts that seem to go in the direction, or in opposition, to human results. But these experimental methods suffer from the difficulty of the rewarding scheme, which can seriously bias or change animal's decision and learned procedure.

In this work, I present a method combining a rewarding scheme with psychophysics adaptive algorithms that allows to measure psychophysical functions also in illusory percepts. I further argue that this method can be applied in some designs without necessity of control trials and also that it allows to measure behavioural biases of any type (sensory, cognitive, decision, etc.) in experiments where adaptive algorithm can be used.

Methods in behavioural research and illusory percepts

Psychophysical measures of sensory systems, e.g. detection thresholds of sound, light, touch or taste, can be classified in two general methodologies: method of constant stimuli or adaptive methods [14,15]. The experimenter has also the choice between different response types for the subject (detection, discrimination, categorization, etc., see [14,15]). For the case of interest presented here, basic sensory measures where a single physical attribute of the stimulus is varied on a continuum scale, the method of forced-choice with two alternatives together with an adaptive algorithm will be used.

When measuring a misperception effect or illusion conditions, the human subject is instructed of the task required by him/her and no feedback about response correctness is allowed during the measures. The no-feedback is done in order to avoid cognitive biases due to perception-feedback interactions and thus allows to measure the subjective perceptual bias when compared to the physical value. A concrete example is the tilt illusion effect, where the orientation of a simple stimulus as a line segment or Gabor patch surrounded by other orientated stimuli is misperceived (Fig.1) [16-20]. This example is used throughout this short method paper for clarifying the important points. In this case, the task of the subject will be to respond whether the orientation of

the target in the centre of the stimulus is tilted counter-clockwise/clockwise (CCW/CW) from their inner vertical reference, respectively defined as categories A and B.

Psychometric function and misperception effects

The psychometric function relates the subject responses to the independent variable of the stimulus, the physical dimension that is varied by the experimenter, and in the example it is defined as the physical orientation of the target vs. the proportion of responses "category B" (CW). This function is monotonous and has asymptotes 0 and 1 (if the subject does not have lapses, Fig.2A) [21], its spread defines the discrimination ability of the subject, and its midpoint gives the point of subjective equality, that is, the stimulus value perceived as the reference, here vertical orientation. If the subject has no perceptual or response bias, a control condition will provide the midpoint of the measured function to be at the physical reference value (up to the measurement error). This means that the subject inner vertical reference is the true physical vertical orientation. In the example of Fig.2A the midpoint should be at 0 degrees (black solid curve). When an experimental configuration with misperception effect is taken, the effect on the psychometric function is to shift its midpoint indicating a bias of perception (Fig.2A, red solid curve, corresponding to stimulus design depicted in right panel of Fig.1). It is readily understood when considering the response of the subject to a target with true vertical orientation: in the example the proportion of responses "category B" is about 0.1, demonstrating the bias.

Adaptive method for psychometric function measure

Adaptive method, or staircase, consists of deciding about staircase's next presented stimulus given the stimuli and responses of the subject at the present trial or past trials of that algorithm [22,23]. Originally, it was used to target one particular point of proportion "correct" responses (p_c) on the psychometric function and its associated stimulus value, but this property is not systematic [24], and now the accumulated data are commonly used for fitting a psychometric function model [21,22].

Many adaptive algorithms are available and here the weighted up-down algorithm is taken [25]. Its rule for a single algorithm is as follows: after each subject response, the stimulus value is modified by an amount S_{up} toward "category B" if subject answer was "category A" and an amount S_{down} toward "category A" if subject response was "category B". The theoretical convergence point on the psychometric function is then $p_c = S_{up} / (S_{up} + S_{down})$. Experimenter fixes the starting value of the algorithm, i.e. the first presented stimulus, the required convergence point, one of the two steps, and the stopping criteria; for the tilt illusion example, two staircases with symmetric convergence points are used for each psychometric function measure, with starting points ± 8 degrees, $p_c = 0.75$ or 0.25 , S_{down} of 1 or 3 degrees, and

Figure 1: Example stimuli for Tilt Illusion tests. The centre Gabor patch, with vertical orientation (0 degrees), is surrounded by a tilted grating (here ± 20 degrees tilts) that induces misperception of the centre orientation.

stopping criteria was a fixed number of trials n (30) for each independent staircase.

It is important to note that, because of the possibility that during the experiment the subject discovers the underlying algorithm [26] and subsequently modifies his response criteria, careful experimental design has to be used when such algorithms are applied. For this reason, multiple adaptive algorithms must be used in parallel and randomly presented from trial-to-trial during the experiment [26], which avoids this learning and criteria change. A second point to consider is the number of responses category A/B of the subject, which if not equal can also create response bias. This is easily solved by designing the experiment such that the number of responses category A/B are equal, for example by using adaptive algorithms converging to symmetrically placed convergence points (if one algorithm targets p_{c1} then a second algorithm must target $p_{c2} = 1 - p_{c1}$).

An example of Monte-Carlo simulation of a simultaneous measure of control and tilt illusion condition is presented in Fig.2, with two staircases per psychometric function converging to 0.75 and 0.25 proportion responses, and 30 trials per algorithm. In Fig.2A the solid black and red curves represent the putative discrimination functions of the subject, with the midpoints at 0.5 proportion representing the theoretical target perceived as "vertical". All four independent staircase algorithms are presented randomly across trials within one experimental session; their Monte-Carlo results are depicted in Fig.2B,C for each condition, respectively.

Two general points are of interest. First, any staircase converges to a point on the psychometric function, and wanders around it with an algorithmically controlled Brownian motion, without any prior knowledge from experimenter where the exact transition part of the function is located on the stimulus dimension. Therefore, methods with adaptive algorithms allow to measure the subjective percept of the subject and it quantifies any changes of percept due to experimental manipulation. Second, convergence around a point p_c has a consequence that the expected mean number of responses "category B" is $p_c \times n$ and responses "category A" is $(1 - p_c) \times n$.

Standard animal reward method and visual illusion condition

When an experiment with an animal is set-up for a behavioural study, the animal is generally trained beforehand on the required task. During training and experimental measures, the animal is rewarded for correct responses and do not receive reward for incorrect responses; correct responses are defined with respect to the physical attribute of interest in the experiment and some reference point along that dimension. At the beginning of training, the animal task is easy (generally starting with eye fixation training) and difficulty level is increased (adding new tasks as lever touch or release and later more complex tasks) until all necessary steps of the experiment are learned and a plateau of no improvement is reached concerning the relevant task in the experiment [6,7,27]. For the tilt illusion example, in the final step a monkey would be rewarded if a lever is rotated clockwise for clockwise tilts of a target stimulus from vertical orientation, and counter-clockwise lever rotation for counter-clockwise tilts of a target stimulus from physical vertical.

Let us consider now the total reward received by an animal and the method used to present the stimuli. If the method of constant stimuli is applied on a control condition for orientation perception (Fig.2A, black curve), the total animal reward rate will be function of the stimuli chosen by the experimentalist and the discrimination capacity of the animal. For example, if the animal has a discrimination threshold of 3 degrees (here defined as the necessary stimulus amount to go from $p=0.5$ to $p=0.84$ on the psychometric function) and seven stimuli are chosen evenly spaced between -3 and +3 degrees (0 is vertical, "+" are clockwise tilts), the animal will receive a mean reward rate near 71%. If the experimenter increases (decreases) the scale tested, this rate will correspondingly increase (decrease). If this method of constant stimuli is used also in a condition with misperception as the tilt illusion and if the animal has this illusory percept, the method will not work because the animal will get confused between what it has learned to respond and what it perceives and will try to adjust its response criteria for increasing its reward [1,27]. For example, assuming the animal has misperception of 3 degrees (Fig.2A, red curve), which should be its subjective vertical, at this value it has a theoretical proportion of response 0.5 for both categories. But the animal would be rewarded only for clockwise responses and this would induce confusion in its response criteria.

If an adaptive method is used for presenting the stimuli, but the reward to the animal is still adjusted to the physical value of the stimulus, the issue with the illusory condition remains.

Reward method for measuring the animal's percept

Since "correct" can not be defined in illusory conditions, one cannot reward any more for the "correct choice of physical value of the stimulus". A different strategy is needed. Here, it is proposed that, for one

Figure 2: Illustration of control and illusory condition measures. (A) Theoretical psychometric functions for a control condition (no tilt illusion; solid black sigmoid) and illusory condition (solid red sigmoid) with an orientation misperception of 3 degrees. Black dots/red crosses are pooled Monte-Carlo results of an experimental measurement (depicted in B-C). (B-C) Visualisation of the staircase adaptive algorithm measures (Monte-Carlo simulations) for two convergence points of 0.75 and 0.25 on each psychometric function (triangles for $p_c=0.25$; dots for $p_c=0.75$; filled symbols represent rewarded responses); (B) for the control condition and (C) for the tilt misperception condition.

given adaptive algorithm the modification consists of defining reward responses as either "category A" or "category B" responses, depending on the convergence point p_c of the algorithm and corresponding to the expected highest proportion. For an algorithm targeting $p_c > 0.5$ the animal will be rewarded only for responses "category B", and vice versa if $p_c < 0.5$. This provides the animal with a high level of reward, with an expected mean reward rate p_c for a single adaptive algorithm. It is important to note that, for the moment, this method should be applied once the animal has properly learned the task during the initial training phase.

Now, the main issues are the balance of the two category responses across the experimental session and the possible discovery by the subject of the underlying algorithm [26], which will induce response criteria change during the course of the experiment. Since it is known that an animal can modify its response criteria during the course of the experiment for reward maximization [1,27], it is very likely that a single adaptive al-

gorithm will be discovered. The solution consists to randomly present at least two algorithms (preferably more) with symmetric convergence points for response equilibration. Thus, the animal will receive globally equal reward for both possible responses and each individual algorithm will be difficult to infer. In the example of tilt illusion measure, for stimuli presented with the algorithm targeting $p_{c1}=0.75$ the animal will receive reward only for CW responses (category B), while for stimuli presented with the algorithm targeting $p_{c2}=0.25$ reward is given only for CCW responses (category A) (see Fig.2B,C, filled symbols on each staircase run).

Selection of the convergence points

From the above description it is understood that the combination of convergence points and number of responses for the categories must be carefully considered. First, as noted earlier, when selecting all convergence points of a session one must consider whether a biased response scheme is of interest (for example research in decision/cognitive biases, by selecting convergence points p_c 's such that their mean is not 50%). In the case of illusory percepts and misperceptions an equilibrium of 50% responses for both categories is necessary to avoid decision biases and thus measure the percept. Second, the total mean reward an animal receives can be adjusted to higher or lower levels by choosing the convergence points. Importantly, this reward will be globally the same across experimental conditions of one session, independently of the subjective perception of the animal.

A note of caution

The method has one point about which the experimenter must be careful. If, by some stochastic motion, a staircase with target point $p_c \neq 0.5$ wanders too far on the opposite side of the psychometric function (i.e. far to the opposite category side), where the percept of the animal is clearly far from the reference (e.g. above 95% correct discrimination), then the animal will not receive reward, that is, positive feedback, when giving the perceptually correct response. Thus, the experimenter needs to carefully choose each algorithm starting point and step size, for example based on literature reports of perceptual measures or some preliminary tests. Another possibility is to use Bayesian adaptive algorithms that target a given point on the psychometric function [28-30], though one should check the stimulus path across trials

Figure 3: Examples of distribution of stimulus levels for each algorithm. (A,B) staircases examples replotted from Fig.2(C,D) with its corresponding psychometric function, overlaid. (C,D) Histograms of visited stimulus levels for each algorithm, open bars for $p_c=0.25$ and filled bars for $p_c=0.75$, presented in (A,B) respectively, with 50,000 trials staircase runs and step size of 1 degree. (E,F) Same as in (C,D) but stimulus step size of 0.5 degrees.

for the above issue. Nevertheless, a session design with random presentation of multiple adaptive algorithms, as already discussed earlier [26], should improve such issues by decreasing its overall probability within experimental runs.

To make the point clear, Fig.3(A,B) replots the staircase runs of the simulated experiment from Fig.2(B,C). In this particular example we see that at most one trial per staircase was tested on the opposite side of the midpoint. Carrying a much longer algorithm run of 50,000 trials/staircase, it was obtained that in this experimental design $\sim 9.5\%$ of the trials are on the opposite side of the midpoint (e.g. for $p_c=0.75$, there are $\sim 9.5\%$ of stimuli below 0/+3 degrees for the black/red curve; Fig.3(C,D)). If the step size is halved, the percentage drops to $\sim 5.8\%$ (Fig.3(E,F)). Since a clear discriminable percept is when on nearly all trials to a stimulus the response is only one category, i.e. near the asymptote, the above examples show that the method should be rather robust to unwanted stochastic wandering. And this will be even more robust when multiple staircase runs are randomly intertwined across trials of a single measurement session.

In the above example one particular and simple algorithm was considered. The experimenter should carry some preliminary work for assessing what algorithm is the most interesting for the tests he/she wants to perform. Furthermore, it should be noted that the adaptive algorithm can be further improved through trial-by-trial Bayesian/Maximum likelihood estimated in order to

check that next trial stimulus is within the appropriate range (e.g. has not crossed the midpoint).

Need of control trials ? Not necessarily

One already used possibility in some visual illusion designs is that one can measure in an unbiased manner the illusory conditions without necessarily introducing control conditions within the experimental session. We can take a look at the example displayed in Fig.1 that depicts two surround conditions known to create opposite effects onto the perception of the central target. On the left panel, the surround makes the centre orientation perceived tilted more CW from vertical, while the right panel makes the centre target perceived tilted more CCW. Therefore, one can use these two conditions within one experimental session, presented randomly and with at least two staircases per condition as described earlier (see Fig.2). Their overall effect is twice the expected effect of each single condition. Such an experimental strategy was already used in psychophysics experiments with humans to avoid plausible cognitive/decision biases from a limited set of contextual stimuli [31,32]. Consequently, it is possible to create measurements of misperception conditions where one does not need a control condition, but simply to counterbalance measures of conditions expected to lead to opposite effects on perceptual outcome.

Application to cognitive and decision biases

While the presentation throughout the manuscript was limited to perceptual biases of illusory type, it should be noted that higher level bias effects, cognitive or decision based, should also be measurable with a proper application of the method; for example, attentional deployment, decision biases due to contextual cueing, decision biases due to asymmetrical motor output (biased rewarding scheme, preferentially rewarding one category), etc.

Conclusion

To conclude, the proposed modification, to use adaptive algorithms and changing the reward scheme to follow only the response type with the highest probability for each single adaptive algorithm, is intuitive and easy to implement. It opens new perspectives on measurements and comparisons between behavioural and neurophysiological measures, especially in conditions with biases, which are expected to bring important insights into exact neurophysiological processes, from sensory levels to decisions and actions.

The presentation of the method was constrained to one modality, vision, and a classical misperception effect was used, the tilt illusion. The application of this method to other visual features, or sensory systems, or cognitive tasks, or different experimental designs, should be readily adapted by researchers to experiments with various animals.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares that he is currently working for his own company (scientific and technical services on psychophysics and modeling of perceptual systems). Thus, the research presented in this work might be considered as having commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest, e.g. for providing services on the topic of the manuscript or patents.

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